

The Influence of Travel Vlogs on Millennials' Decisions to Visit Local Travel Destinations

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Abstract: Before the digital era, tourists relied on magazines, brochures, and television for travel information. In contrast to travel blogs and vlogs, travelers can get more definitive information from vloggers who share first-hand experiences. The research generally aimed to determine the effect of travel vlogs on millennials' decision-making when it comes to traveling around the Philippines. The research was descriptive and aimed to describe a population, occurrence, or event accurately and scrutinizingly. The research used structured questionnaires and exploratory data analysis to gather and analyze data and identify possible connections between variables. Travel vlogs boost a destination's credibility and reputation, according to the researchers' findings. After visiting a destination, thinking about it, and evaluating it, people are more likely to want to return.

Keywords: Travel vlogs, Travel destination, Millennials, Travel vloggers, Travel motivators.

1. INTRODUCTION

The usage of the Internet has been preeminent in the tourism industry, while travel influencers have become an effective way for several hospitality businesses to interact with their target market and create brand recognition. At present, the tourism industry cannot be relied upon without the opinion of travel vlogs—which play a huge role in the publicity of destinations (Abad & Borbon, 2021). However, during the past few years, destination management organizations (DMOs) have seen less monetary support from the government and have become more dependent on commercial revenue to fund their main activities (Li et al., 2017).

Before the digital era, tourists depended on the traditional media as a mode of communication from tourism providers through magazines, brochures, and television. In contrast to travel blogs and vlogs, individuals are exposed to different visual cues or symbols in which an interested traveler can get more definitive information as the vlogger is sharing first-hand experience, wherein it shows the actual picture of what travelers can experience and that establishes a destination image in the mind of the traveler (Choi et al. 2018).

Travel vloggers can be considered social influencers in destination marketing because of their travel stories being shared online, resulting in feedback from their followers, leading to persuasion or inspiration to travel to the same destination. Because travel vlogs are created by travelers who are at the destination, they are likely to endorse the location and highlight its key features. This could be thought of as a personal recommendation on the part of the travel vloggers.

As a result, travel vloggers, who are considered social influencers, may be a useful destination marketing tool due to their greater reach to the target market than other marketing platforms. This is clearly reflected in the improving local tourism activity, vis a vis the increasing popularity of travel vlogs, whether independent or sponsored. Despite the numerous challenges in creating vlogs, these methods provide the traveler a closer look at their destination of choice as those are known to be unpredictable, shifting every now and then, which so necessitates the industry to foster these evolving expectations.

Online destination image, according to Mak (2017, p. 282), is the online delineation of shared beliefs, feelings, and general intuitions about a destination. Digital technologies make it feasible for online destination images to be established and distributed. Moreover, online destination images may be cataloged as projected and discerned online destination images.

The characteristics gauged through marketing communications, such as the Department of Tourism's websites, that exhibit the "absolute" attributes of the destination are referred to as the "projected online destination image." On the other hand, the discerned online destination image is the aggregated impressions, discernments, and feelings that tourists share virtually regarding tourism products and offerings in a destination. The Philippines' online destination image is created and carried by the vloggers, and vlogs are seen as perceived online destination images.

The desire to learn while traveling is a trait of the millennial generation. They search out distinctive, engaging experiences and personable locations (Hamed, 2017). Since it has been established that travelers form much stronger connections with tourist destinations when they are humanized and endowed with a soul, the idea of destination personality—defined as destination branding through the use of personal traits and characteristics typical of humans—has been widely used in marketing for a long time. (Starcevi et al., 2017).

Millennials value environmentally friendly goods and locations as tourists (Bochert et al., 2017). Due to their belief that traveling has a purpose and contributes to a better future, they are also frequently referred to as "cause activists." Millennials also like "volunteer tourism," which involves visiting and volunteering in underserved social communities (Veiga et al., 2017). Therefore, one option for travel providers is to include such activities in their offers as a section that could enhance the customer experience, as they are likely to participate in sustainability and environmental protection activities throughout their trips (Hamed, 2017).

It is not only because of the emergence of the digital era as to why consumers depend on online media as a reliable source of information but also for the following reasons: (1) only travel providers provide all the information and not a required endowment between both travel providers and travelers, as with this, travelers can also bestow based on their own interests; (2) online media creates a destination image, which prompts excitement that results in the consumer's purchase decision; (3) tourists can depend on feedback and comments because they can use this information to organize correspondingly and refine their travel experience (Azucena & Nandakumar, 2020).

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

The diagram above reveals the factors that can trigger the influence of travelers to travel to local places after they watched a travel vlogger which are the Vlogger's attractiveness, Perceptual interactivity, Perceived enjoyment, and Perceived usefulness to travel. These factors will help the study to determine the traveler's perspective when choosing a travel vlog to watch and for the travel vloggers on how they can gain more influence.

Moreover, the researchers would be able to measure the willingness of a traveler is looking for its presumed effect. With the help of factors mentioned above, it will help the study determine the willingness of a traveler.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study aimed to gauge how millennials are being influenced by various travel vlogs being uploaded on the Internet in choosing a travel destination to visit in the Philippines. In particular, the researchers sought answers to these questions and came up with a strong conclusion by the end of the study.

Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

[1.] What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

[1.1] Age

[1.2] Gender

[1.3] Educational Attainment

[1.4] Frequency of Travel

[2.] What is the respondent's assessment on the travel vlog in terms of:

[2.1] Vlogger's attractiveness

[2.2] Perceived Information Credibility

[2.3] Perceived enjoyment

[2.4] Perceived value for money

[2.5] Perceived usefulness

[3.] Is there a significant difference on the assessment of the respondents when grouped according to demographic profile?

[4] Based on the results and findings, what recommendations can the researchers give to travel vloggers to enhance their travel vlogs.

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESIS

The statement of the null hypothesis in this study was: There is no significant relationship between the factors (quality of the post, user experience, and people reached) that measure the effectiveness of social media.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY (OS)

The research generally aimed to determine the effect of travel vlogs on millennials' decision-making when it comes to traveling around the Philippines. Specifically, the researchers also aimed to distinguish the importance of travel vloggers and their respective vlogs in the increase of foreign and local travelers visiting the country. The accumulated data from the respondents may become a basis for the Department of Tourism and the local government units to stabilize the Philippines' tourism industry through travel vlogs.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Tourism and Social Media Technology

Today, social media has made information about the product known quickly to other consumers who have purchased and made use of the product. This information can be in the form of text, photos, audio files, or videos. (Mamori et al. 2020).

YouTube is one of the most prominent social media sites with video content containing video advertisements, clips, reviews, tutorials, and even daily life about the efflux of video makers. It is one of the first choices of several people because it is one source of social media information that has various benefits. First, content consisting of videos can be accepted by the public without causing any problems. Second, the platform supports all online-based devices, which means it can support a tremendous number of viewers. Lastly, Youtube features such as posted videos can be searched using keywords and hashtags, which are all characteristics that can make it accessible for respondents to find the information they seek. A large number of videos available on Youtube activities is a likely resource for information restoration. (Mamori et al. 2020).

Because of their huge marketing potential, travel vlogs have received increasing attention from hospitality and tourism researchers. A study was conducted among the local tourists of Oman, and the researchers found out that the majority of

them depend on social media technology for information about picturesque destinations in the country. Al-Badi et al. (2017) found that people's travel decisions are affected by what people say about a place on social media. These people also encourage the Ministry of Tourism to use social media to increase local tourism.

Another study was conducted, and it was found that video marketing, such as vlogs, can influence customers more than any other mode (Vermees, 2018). Specifically, photos and videos posted on Youtube are inclined to attract more tourists. In Garut, Indonesia, multilingual vlogs were shot containing local culture. English, Mandarin, and German were the languages used in the videos. These vlogs were posted on YouTube, Instagram, and other sites. Purwadi et al. (2017) found that they were useful not only for foreign tourists but also for local tourists.

Tourism and Travel Influencers

Social media influencers are extremely exposed to the digital world of social networks. These people are seen as having a significant influence on public decisions. They can influence what products to buy, which services to use, and what initiatives to support (Zeljko et al., 2018). This influential power can translate to marketing physical products. It can shift the global economy and sway politics. This shows how social media influencers can change how future travelers think about sustainable travel options.

Social media influencers are different from traditional celebrities. They must develop a personal brand through their work and a sense of uniqueness. SMEs work to develop their own brand and extend their potential fame. They work to create close and consistent relationships with fans by sharing parts of their lives online (Kay et al. 2020). These online relationships are also known as interactions (Daniel et al. 2018). Social media influencers with a high number of followers are known as microcelebrities (Jorge et al. 2018). As a matter of fact, microcelebrity is a new type of influential celebrity. Microcelebrity deploys a communicative practice by creating a public persona that strategically interacts with the viewers intimately (Jorge et al. 2018).

Travel vlogs, as the most well-known type of travel video watched on Youtube according to Henderson (2018), were found to give audiences a more entertaining viewing experience and develop more business possibilities for influencers or microcelebrities. Previous studies have analyzed the aftermath of microcelebrity endorsements on customers' hotel booking objectives (Zhang et al. 2019). Gretzel (2017) also pointed out how likely it is for businesses or organizations to work with influencers to promote hotel brands and destinations.

As more attractions and accommodations move online, budgets to publicize a destination seem to dwindle. Social media is one method that is cost-effective with substantial reach. In terms of tourism, social media is the ultimate weapon for publicity and awareness. However, these SMIs must strike a balance between authenticity, sponsorships, culture, and levels of engagement (Woodcock & Johnson, 2019). Therefore, quality and successful social media influencers must be invested in well to have the greatest impact on future travel.

Vlogger's Attractiveness

An attractive appearance has a positive effect on the extent to which audiences want to become that character (Arunrangsiwed et al. 2018). According to Tolbert and Drogos (2019), female Youtubers are gauged as more attractive and popular than males, whereas male Youtubers are appraised as more vicious than females. Also, according to the researchers, young girls like and form closeness with female content creators over males, and vice versa.

Perceived Information Credibility

Among the research contexts into travel videos that interprets naturalistic data or the content of both travel vlogs and the audience's comments towards them, Youtube appears to be a well-known research context. Briciu and Briciu (2020) used descriptive analysis to demonstrate the typical patterns in the number of likes, shares, and comments on travel vlogs, which is a prognosis of participatory culture. Cheng et al. (2020) say that travel vlogs are becoming more and more important for promoting destinations to potential markets.

Xu et al. (2021) argued that using data from a commenting system like that of Youtube is laborious. A fundamental reason is that this system can neither categorically associate viewers' answers to video content nor guarantee the rapidity of such responses. By scrutinizing the comments of a vlog, researchers cannot cite the video content that the viewer mentions. This problem has been inscribed, however, in Bili Bili, a Chinese social media platform that offers viewers a chance to comment on vlogs while simultaneously watching (Yang, 2019). This action is similar to an audience reacting to a live performance

in theater or stage productions, shouting out their comments in reaction to particular actions on stage. Consequently, the system provides evidence to connect audiences' participation with video content.

While Implicit Association Tests are mostly used to find out about stereotypes and preconceived notions, the main methodological ideas are the same for bullet comments. For example, tourists' quick answers to video content show a more honest and genuine response from them (Xu et al., 2021).

Perceived Enjoyment

Resonance is the usual notion characterized by people's connections to messages. In the context of travel vlogs, it is an experience during which viewers feel a personal connection with vloggers and the information they carry (Giorgi, 2017). It has been used across regulations, including "cultural resonance, personified resonance, emotional resonance, behavioral resonance, formed resonance, and historical resonance" (Ruthven, 2020).

Fellowship and consistency are the prerequisites of the resonance experience arising through watching travel vlogs. Familiarity or fellowship is important because it demonstrates the role that audiences have already given credence to and experienced, while also laying the groundwork for audiences to accept what is new.

Resonance is divided into two: logical and emotional. Logical resonance happens when content meets the viewers' values, reliance, and understandings; on the other hand, emotional resonance happens when the content becomes of interest to the audiences' feelings, affection, and yearnings (Giorgi, 2017; Cheng et al. 2020). The connection between emotional and logical resonance is more like passing into each other. Giorgi (2017) chooses to consider that emotional and logical resonance are unanimously fortifying in establishing the relationship between travel vlogs and audiences.

Travel Motivators

Another local study conducted in Lyceum of the Philippines University Batangas from Sta Cruz, Laguna, indicated the influence of travel vlogs in terms of the decision-making process of the respondents in Laguna. People tend to be affected by travel vloggers, especially when the information from a certain vlog is credible. Findings also showed that cognitive, emotional, and epistemic values are the leading factors why people tend to be impacted by travel vlogs (Abad & Borbon 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY

Study Method and Design

Research was a quantitative design where the researchers analyzed different variables while including numbers as well as statistics in a project to scrutinize its results. In particular, the researchers utilized a descriptive study, which aims to describe a population, occurrence, or event accurately and scrutinizingly. It can answer questions starting with what, where, when, and how, but not why questions. According to McCombes (2022), a descriptive study can use a broad range of methods to examine multiple variables. Unlike in experimental research, the researcher does not control or exploit any of the variables, but only observes and measures them.

Instrumentation

The research used structured questionnaires in accumulating the data. The act of reviewing a process or querying a selected sample of individuals to acquire data about a service, product, or process is referred to as a survey. Data gathering surveys are used to gather information on a certain group of people's attitudes, conduct, or expertise. Written questionnaires, face-to-face or telephone interviews, focus groups, and electronic (e-mail or internet) surveys are all examples of surveys. Surveys are a good way to collect and analyze data, and they are often used with important stakeholders, like customers and workers, to find out what they need and how satisfied they are (ASQ, n.d.).

Sampling Technique

The researchers made use of a cluster sampling technique and the Raosoft calculator to determine the number of respondents to gather data from. In cluster sampling, researchers separate a population into smaller groups or clusters, and then they aimlessly select among these clusters to form a sample. Cluster sampling is also both time and cost-efficient, particularly for samples that are broadly geographically scattered and would be hard to correctly sample otherwise. If the population is

clustered accurately, a study will have high external authenticity because the sample will consider the characteristics of the larger population. (Thomas, 2021)

The Raosoft calculator can be used to estimate an ideal sample size based on a desired margin of error, desired confidence level, and response distribution. The researchers decided to conduct a questionnaire with 150 millennials between the ages of 18 and 25. The sample size was 73 respondents, with a desired confidence level of 95%, a 5% margin of error, and a 90% response distribution.

The Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers created a close-ended survey questionnaire through Google Forms, some of which can be answered by yes or no or are provided with a multiple choice. On the first page of Google Forms, the participants were given a consent form that allows the researchers to collect replies from the selected participants. The survey questionnaires were divided into two (2) parts:

1. Influence of Travel Vloggers' Popularity in Choosing a Travel Destination to Visit
2. The Influence of Social Media Sites in Choosing a Travel Destination to Visit

The survey was open for 15 days, and once everyone had filled out their forms, the results were added up, tabulated, and analyzed.

Data Analysis

The research went through exploratory data analysis, commonly known as EDA. It is the process of using numerical synopsis and vision to explore the data and distinguish possible connections between variables. With this type of data analysis, researchers may find inconsistencies in their data, such as strange observations. They may also find patterns, understand possible correlations between variables, and come up with interesting questions or hypotheses that they can test in the future using more formal statistical methods.

The researchers used dispersion methods, mainly ANOVA, to analyze the data. The ANOVA test allows for the diversification of more than two groups at the same time to determine whether a relationship occurs between them. The F ratio, the ANOVA formula's result, enables the study of several groupings of data to evaluate the unevenness between and within samples (Kenton, 2021). The formula for ANOVA is:

$$F = \frac{MST}{MSE}$$

wherein:

F = ANOVA coefficient

MST = Mean sum of squares due to treatment

MSE = Mean sum of squares due to error

Likert scale was used for verbal interpretation of the mean value.

Mean Value	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 - 4.00	4	Strongly agree
2.50-3.24	3	Agree
1.75-2.49	2	Disagree
1.00-1.74	1	Strongly Disagree

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the demographic profile of the respondents and the influences of travel vlogs on millennials' decision-making. A total of 73 responded to the survey questionnaire on the influence of travel vlogs on millennials' decisions to visit local travel destinations from July 06–July 20, 2022.

Table 1.1 Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
25 - 30 years old	55	75.3
30-35 years old	9	12.3
35 - 40 years old	9	12.3
Total	73	100.0

The study revealed that in Table 1.1, out of 73 respondents, 75.3% belonged to the under 25–30-year-old age bracket and got the highest rank. 12.3% are under 30-35 and 35-40 years old, with the same percentage and receiving the lowest.

The research indicated that most of the respondents belong to the 25–30 age bracket, which means that they are still trying to explore and belong to the millennial category. Millennials are still young and want to seek their potential to travel. Lifestyle is also a factor to consider when traveling that pushes most of them to visit local places, especially around their area. (Ramadania, 2021).

Table 1.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	39	53.4
Male	34	46.6
Total	73	100.0

The study revealed that in Table 1.2, out of 73 respondents, 53.4% are female while 46.6% are male.

According to a study by (Zhumadilova. 2020), travel television shows and travel vlogs contribute information to the viewers in providing pleasing destinations and tourist services.

In Zhumadilova's findings, it shows that male respondents appeared to be more interested in watching travel-related television shows and travel vlogs. However, female respondents showed that they were mainly utilizing the influence of travel vlogs and tended to have actual travel experiences because of travel vlogs. As a result, females utilized the advertised tourism services more frequently in the video content than males.

Table 1.3 Educational Attainment

Education Attainment	Frequency	Percent
College Graduate	50	68.5
Senior High School Graduate	8	11.0
Undergraduate	15	20.5
Total	73	100.0

The study revealed that in Table 1.3, out of 73 respondents, 68.5% are college graduates with educational attainment and got the highest score. 20.5% are undergraduates and received the second highest score, while 11.0% are high school seniors and received the lowest score.

2. What is the respondents' assessment of the travel vlog in terms of:

[2.1] Vlogger's attractiveness

[2.2] Perceived Information Credibility

[2.3] Perceived Enjoyment

[2.4] Perceived Value for Money

[2.5] Perceived Usefulness

Table 2.1 Vlogger's Attractiveness

Descriptives	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variable Interpretation	Rank
1. The vlogger's attitude is well mannered in other nature.	4.068	0.871	Strongly Agree	2
2. The vloggers are very interesting, funny, and very relatable.	4.233	0.773	Strongly Agree	1
3. The vlogger feels a lot like me	3.685	0.998	Strongly Agree	4
4. The vlogger looks good	4.014	0.842	Strongly Agree	3
5. The vlogger's behavior is very similar to mine.	3.603	0.982	Strongly Agree	5
Over-all mean	3.921		Strongly Agree	

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The study revealed that in Table 2.1, the highest rank that accumulated a mean of 4.233, the respondents strongly agreed that vloggers are very interesting, funny, and relatable. While the lowest ranked person accumulated a mean of 3.603, the respondents disagreed that vloggers' behavior is very similar to their behavior. Overall, with regards to Vloggers' attractiveness, it accumulated a mean of 3.921 with the verbal interpretation of "Agree."

The research indicated that vloggers' attractiveness highly agrees on the humor and how relatable their content is, which means that the vlogger's attractiveness influences millennials' travel decisions. With this, travel vloggers have been a huge motivator for viewers, mainly because of their physical experience. They share their journey during the trip, which also has a positive impact on viewers' travel decisions because of their relatable experiences. (Sizan et al. 2022).

Moreover, Pearce et al. (2021) indicated that content categories such as humor and tourist experiences make it more interesting and funnier, and they give the audience involvement to have intentions of traveling while watching travel vlogs.

Table 2.2 shows the mean, standard deviation, verbal interpretation, and rank of travel vlogs' perceived information credibility for millennials.

Table 2.2 Perceived Information Credibility

Descriptives	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variable Interpretation	Rank
1. Most reviews and comments are positive.	4.082	0.829	Strongly Agree	3
2. Travel vloggers show the current and up-to-date information.	4.288	0.808	Strongly Agree	1.5
3. Travel vloggers are well-traveled.	4.288	0.772	Strongly Agree	1.5
4. Travel vloggers present detailed content about the destination.	4.164	0.850	Strongly Agree	2
5. Travel vloggers show his/her sources of information.	4.041	0.934	Strongly Agree	4
Over-all mean	4.173		Strongly Agree	

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The study revealed that Table 2.2. shows that the highest rank accumulated a mean of 4.288. The respondents strongly agree that when the vloggers are currently up to date about the information and the vloggers are well traveled, the second highest rank is when the vloggers show detailed content about the destination, which accumulated a mean of 4.164. The third rank accumulated a mean of 4.082, which the most reviews and comments are positive. The last and the lowest rank is when the vlogger shows his/her sources of information that accumulated a mean of 4.041. Overall, with regards to the up-to-date information, it accumulated a total of 4.173 with the verbal interpretation of "agree."

Travel vlogs are said to have increased a destination's perceived reputation and given it legitimacy. A live journey, thoughts, and evaluations combine to produce a realistic experience that makes people want to travel to the said destination. The goal of this study is to investigate the potential of travel vlogs for destination promotion. Residents of Sta. Cruz, Laguna were the subjects of the study. While the correlational technique was utilized to evaluate the link between the elements influencing the decision-making process and visitors' destination choice, the descriptive design gave a general overview of real cognition, feelings, and actions within the group. A researcher-made to ascertain each variable's level of influence, a questionnaire was used. The findings showed that people tend to be influenced by travel vloggers more so when making decisions linked to travel, especially when it comes to considering reliable information. The research also demonstrated that vloggers significantly influenced travelers' decisions in terms of cognitive, emotional, and epistemic values. There is also a considerable correlation between the quality of travel-related decisions and the selection of the location. Finally, the study created a destination model that advises Laguna Tourism on how to improve and maintain destination quality.

Travel blogs have become a significant source of travel knowledge. Bloggers share their travel experiences and are typically regarded as reliable sources of information. They affect readers' opinions and perceptions of different locations, which has an impact on travel choices. Despite the significance of bloggers as influencers, little is known about the factors that impact their decision to blog about travel destinations. This is the focus of our study, which gets information from conversations with Turkish travel bloggers. The interviews covered topics such as bloggers' motivations, the presence of collaboration, and bloggers' perspectives on their influencer roles. Since a greater understanding of these elements might aid destinations in better blog marketing, the research has significant implications for theory and practice.

Table 2.3 Perceived Enjoyment

Descriptives	Mean	Standard Variable	Deviation	Rank
1.Watching travel vlogging can help relive my stress	4.288	0.964	Strongly Agree	1
2.I watch travel vlogs to enjoy my free time	4.096	1.120	Strongly Agree	3
3.I watch vlogs because it's fun	4.219	0.886	Strongly Agree	2
4.I feel very excited when I watch travel vlog	4.082	1.051	Strongly Agree	4
5.Watching travel vlogs gives me satisfaction	4.068	1.084	Strongly Agree	5
Over-all Mean	4.151		Strongly Agree	

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

The table above shows that the second row, which has an accumulated mean of 4.288, got the highest rank. Whereas the study only proves that watching travel vlogs can help relieve the stress of the viewers or the respondents, On the other hand, the lowest rank has an accumulated mean of 4.068. It only means that the respondents still possibly agree that watching travel vlogs gives them satisfaction.

The study was made to investigate the audience's resonance experience when watching travel vlogs and its influence on their stress relief and perceived enjoyment. The premise of this study was that when the audience's inherent needs are being fulfilled, it would change their perception of enjoyment in watching vlogs. The results revealed that audiences' resonance experiences were significantly related to their continued intention to watch travel vlogs and their travel intention for presented destinations. Also, audiences' resonance experiences were positively related to their perceived involvement, followed by continued intention to watch, and travel intention. (Lee, Wang et al. 2021).

The research outcome showed how young people use travel vlogs to relax and have fun. A wide variety of travel vloggers help people, especially teenage viewers, find a perfect way to release their stress. It also shows how young people themselves feel about the impact of vlogs on them. Also, the author analyzes why this phenomenon takes place. (Yan et al. 2021).

Table 2.4 shows the mean, standard deviation, verbal interpretation, and rank of travel vlogs' perceived value for money for the millennials.

Table 2.4 Perceived Value for Money

Descriptives	Mean	Standard Variable	Deviation	Rank
1. Travel vlogs gives idea how much money to save	4.192	1.009	Strongly Agree	4
2. Travel vlogs gives idea where to book cheap but quality hotels	4.247	0.863	Strongly Agree	2
3. Travel vlogs suggest places, so you don't regret spending your money	4.301	0.794	Strongly Agree	1
4. Travel vlogs helps me to rate products and services	4.233	0.874	Strongly Agree	3
5. Travel vlogs gives convenience and justice for money	4.178	0.977	Strongly Agree	5
Over-all Mean	4.230		Strongly Agree	

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Table 2.4 shows the millennials' perceived value for money upon watching various travel vlogs. The fourth statement, travel vlogs give convenience and justice for money, ranked last with a mean of 4.178 and a variable interpretation of "Strongly Agree," whilst the descriptive that ranked first on the table is the second statement, travel vlogs suggest places, so millennials do not regret spending their money, with a mean of 4.301 and a variable interpretation of "Strongly Agree."

According to Cary (2020), vlogs provide the audience with a sense of what to anticipate during the journey as well as when they arrive at their destination. On YouTube, vlogs that focus on traveling to new locations consistently receive more views and likes than those that cover other topics. Also, it gets four times as much social interaction and has more subscribers than both travel tours and videos and official travel publications. The vlogs that are associated with going to new places become collaborative, which boosts the appeal of the destination. In addition, viewers find it appealing to watch real-life vlogs on YouTube that are about visiting new places because it allows them to connect with the video makers.

Table 2.5 Perceived Usefulness

Descriptives	Mean	Standard Variable	Deviation	Rank
1. Travel vlog feature destinations that are new and places not yet discovered.	4.260	0.817	Strongly Agree	3
2. Content in the travel vlog gives me a more comprehensive grasp of travel information	4.219	0.837	Strongly Agree	4
3. Travel vlog makes travel easier	4.164	0.882	Strongly Agree	5
4. I can get useful information like how to get there, safety, and budget tips by watching travel vlog.	4.397	0.740	Strongly Agree	2
5. Travel vlogs helps tourism industry to grow.	4.493	0.766	Strongly Agree	1
Over-all Mean	4.307		Strongly Agree	

3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree

Table 2.5 shows the millennials' perceived usefulness of travel vlogs. The statement "Content in the travel vlog gives me a more comprehensive grasp of travel information" ranked last with a mean of 4.219 and a variable interpretation of "Strongly Agree," while the statement "Travel vlogs help the tourism industry to grow," ranked first with a mean of 4.493 and a variable interpretation of "Strongly Agree."

Not only do travel vlogs entertain their audience, but they also have a significant impact on the vacations that their audience chooses to take. Each vlog gives a unique take on ethical travel by explaining problematic ideas or systems, promoting multiculturalism, or talking about urgent environmental problems that most mainstream travel vlogs tend to ignore.

The topics of minimalism, travel, and technology are frequently discussed in Josh Fenn's vlogs. Those who are looking to lighten their loads in preparation for long-term travel will find his series entitled "One-Bag-Travel" immensely useful. Additionally, he thrives on product promotion while avoiding the appearance of salesmanship. His series on simple living is good for everyday life, but eco-friendly travelers can use his tips for reducing waste, reusing things, and spending wisely on any trip (Micucci, n.d.).

Another vlogger is Doug Lansky. Unlike Josh Fenn, his commentary on the travel industry, which is also available as a podcast, is both enlightening and unwaveringly straightforward. Lansky offers guidance to public officials, city planners, and private entities on how to address sustainability concerns and battle over tourism (Micucci, n.d.).

3. Is there a significant difference on the assessment of the respondents when grouped according to demographic profile?

3.1 When grouped by Age

Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p
Vlogger's attractiveness	4.055	2	0.1316
Perceived information credibility	3.506	2	0.1732
Perceived enjoyment	5.937	2	0.0514
Perceived value for money	1.561	2	0.4582
Perceived usefulness	2.474	2	0.2902

Descriptives	Age	N	Mean	Median	SD
Vlogger's attractiveness	25 - 30 years old	55	3.840	3.800	0.736
	31 - 35 years old	9	3.956	3.800	0.606
	36 - 40 years old	9	4.378	4.600	0.651
Perceived information credibility	25 - 30 years old	55	4.098	4.200	0.736
	31 - 35 years old	9	4.222	4.000	0.570
	36 - 40 years old	9	4.578	4.800	0.552
Perceived enjoyment	25 - 30 years old	55	4.033	4.200	1.001
	31 - 35 years old	9	4.267	4.200	0.624
	36 - 40 years old	9	4.756	5.000	0.546
Perceived value for money	25 - 30 years old	55	4.196	4.200	0.819
	31 - 35 years old	9	4.178	4.200	0.696
	36 - 40 years old	9	4.489	5.000	0.782

When people watch vloggers or video blogs, they are influenced by five factors that influence their decision to visit nearby attractions. Table 3.1 demonstrates that there is not a significant difference in the opinions of respondents who fall into different age categories regarding these five factors. The observers observed that the value of cash received the highest

probability, which is 0.4582, followed by the observation of handiness, which is 0.2902. Next up is the data validity, which was given a score of 0.1732, and the final two classifications fall anywhere between 0.0514 and 0.316. Arunrangsiwed et al. (2018), who say that a person's alluring appearance emphatically affects the degree to which crowds need to turn into that person, went against the appeal of the vloggers (0.1316), which they found to be appealing. Also, Tolbert and Drogos (2019) found that female YouTube creators are rated as more popular and attractive than male YouTube creators, which led to male YouTube creators being rated as more repulsive than female YouTube creators. However, in terms of the value of money, one strategy that is both practical and has a significant reach is the use of virtual entertainment.

When it comes to the tourism sector, virtual entertainment has emerged as a potent tool for increasing awareness and exposure. Nevertheless, these SMIs ought to locate harmony between validness, sponsorships, culture, and levels of commitment (Woodcock and Johnson, 2019), and this does not demonstrate the aftereffects of the ANOVA. Additionally, according to Cheng et al. (2020), sightseeing video blogs are increasingly playing a part in raising objections to potential business sectors. This runs counter to the findings found in the outcomes given by the ANOVA (Kruskal-Wallis), which is 0.1732 and indicates that there is no significant significance towards the age of viewers when watching video blogs. To put it another way, the age ranges from 25 to 40 years old does not constitute a significant portion of the segment profile that was gathered in the evaluation based on age.

3.2 When grouped by Gender

Independent Samples T-Test

		Statistic	p
Vlogger's attractiveness	Mann-Whitney U	626.500	0.6891
Perceived information credibility	Mann-Whitney U	585.000	0.3879
Perceived enjoyment	Mann-Whitney U	658.500	0.9636
Perceived value for money	Mann-Whitney U	625.500	0.6747
Perceived usefulness	Mann-Whitney U	626.000	0.6789

Descriptives	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD
Vlogger's attractiveness	Female	39	3.892	3.800	0.653
	Male	34	3.953	4.000	0.808
Perceived information credibility	Female	39	4.097	4.200	0.745
	Male	34	4.259	4.300	0.663
Perceived enjoyment	Female	39	4.149	4.200	0.942
	Male	34	4.153	4.500	0.955
Perceived value for money	Female	39	4.251	4.600	0.834
	Male	34	4.206	4.200	0.762
Perceived usefulness	Female	39	4.354	4.400	0.603
	Male	34	4.253	4.400	0.770

Table 3.2 shows that there is not a significant difference in the opinions of respondents from different demographic classes (male and female) regarding the five factors that influence travelers to visit a nearby destination when they watch vloggers travel from different areas. This is shown by the fact that there isn't a significant difference. Because the P-worths of the five classes come in at 0.6891, 0.3879, 0.9636, 0.6747, and 0.6789, respectively, which are all higher than the minimum level of 0.05, we are able to convey that there is no significance with regard to the direction orders. Since the p-value has a p-value that is more unmistakable than the 0.05 level, there is not an enormous qualification in the assessment of the respondents with their various direction groupings on the overall results. This is due to the p-value. It is acceptable to excuse

the false hypothesis that there is not a significant difference. This demonstrated that respondents' direction classes have nothing to do with going to the nearby places to be based on the video that was posted by the vlogger.

In any event, according to the authorities, young children favor and construct closeness with female substance producers over males, as well as the other way around. This preference and construction also apply to older children. The content analysis and the group analysis both suggest that there is a gendered abnormality in both the creation and get-together of video web journals. However, this does not imply that female vloggers are not exactly as truthfully appropriate as male vloggers or that female viewers of video sites feel less like they are a part of an online community. Our discoveries indicate that female vloggers, despite posting on their channels less frequently than men do, will.

3.3 When grouped by Educational Attainment

Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p
Vlogger's attractiveness	0.595	2	0.7428
Perceived information credibility	0.624	2	0.7318
Perceived enjoyment	0.519	2	0.7716
Perceived value for money	0.426	2	0.8082
Perceived usefulness	0.481	2	0.7862

Descriptives	Educational Attainment	N	Mean	Median	SD
Vlogger's attractiveness	College Graduate	50	3.900	4.000	0.726
	Senior High School Graduate	8	3.850	3.700	0.769
	Undergraduate	15	4.027	4.000	0.736
Perceived information credibility	College Graduate	50	4.148	4.100	0.677
	Senior High School Graduate	8	4.300	4.300	0.555
	Undergraduate		4.187	4.200	0.899
Perceived enjoyment	College Graduate	50	4.168	4.300	0.899
	Senior High School Graduate	8	3.950	3.700	0.972
	Undergraduate	15	4.200	4.600	1.108
Perceived value for money	College Graduate	50	4.248	4.200	0.735
	Senior High School Graduate	8	4.100	4.100	0.733
	Undergraduate	15	4.240	4.800	1.045

Table 3.3 shows that the educational attainment of the respondents on the assessment does not have any significant difference across the five categories. According to the Kruskal-Wallis test assessment, the p-values of the five categories are 0.7428, 0.7318, 0.7716, 0.8082, and 0.7862, which are way higher than 0.05. The null hypothesis that there is a significant difference in respondents' educational attainment has nothing to do with the influence of vloggers on them visiting local places in the country. It was also demonstrated that the credibility of the information (0.7318) affects the way of analyzing the data found in the vlogs. Xu et al. (2021) argued that using data from a commenting system like that of Youtube is laborious. A fundamental reason is that this system can neither categorically associate viewers' answers to video content nor guarantee the rapidity of such responses. By scrutinizing the comments of a vlog, researchers cannot cite the video content that the viewer mentions, which makes the educational attainment significant upon scrutinizing the comments of other viewers while watching the vlog. Overall, educational attainment does not have any significant difference across the five categories presented in the paper. This is because of the p-value that each category shows. The significance level is greater than 0.05 percent, so the claim is rejected. And therefore, the respondents, when grouped according to their educational attainments, have nothing to do with whether they want or do not want to visit the place that the vloggers have been showing them.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the data gathered by the researchers, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The researchers found out that the primary viewers of travel vlogs are mostly young females in the age bracket of 25–30 years old and considered college graduates.

2. What is the respondent's assessment on the travel vlog in terms of:

2.1 Vloggers Attractiveness

The respondents concur that vloggers are incredibly intriguing, humorous, and relatable. Research has shown that a vlogger's attractiveness is strongly related to how relatable and funny their content is. This means that the vlogger's attractiveness affects millennials' decisions about where to travel.

2.2 Perceived Information Credibility

Respondents decisively agree that they are enticed to travel when vloggers are knowledgeable about current events and have traveled widely. Travel vlogs are credited with building a destination's validity and improving its perceived reputation. People are more likely to wish to visit a destination after experiencing it firsthand and thinking about it, as well as after thinking about it and evaluating it.

2.3 Perceived Enjoyment

The results have clearly shown how watching travel vlogs can help viewers or respondents feel less stressed. Many different travel vloggers provide viewers, especially teen viewers, a great way to relieve tension. Additionally, it demonstrates how adolescents themselves feel about the influence of vlogs on them all.

2.4 Perceived value for money

The statement, "Travel vlogs advise areas, so millennials do not regret spending their money," is the descriptor that received the highest ranking on the table. Vlogs provide viewers a sense of what to expect both in the process of traveling and once they get there.

2.5 Perceived usefulness

The top response was "Travel vlogs help the tourism industry to grow." Travel vlogs not only amuse their viewers, but they also have a big influence on the types of vacations that viewers decide to take. Each vlog has a different take on what it means to travel ethically by pointing out questionable ideas or systems, promoting multiculturalism, or bringing up important environmental issues that most popular travel vlogs tend to ignore.

3. Significant difference on the assessment of the respondents when grouped according to demographic profile

3.1 When grouped by Age

The researchers found out from the result of the survey that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents from different age groups on the final number of respondents on the influence of travel vlogs. This indicates that respondents with different age groups have the same judgement as the other age group.

3.2 When grouped by Gender

The researchers found out from the result of the survey that there is a no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents from different age groups on the final number of respondents on the influence of travel vlogs. This means that both men and women have the same opinion about how travel vlogs affect the world.

3.3 When grouped by Educational Attainment

The researchers found out from the result of the survey that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents from different age groups on the final number of respondents on the influence of travel vlogs. This concludes that all respondents with different educational attainment have the same assessment of the results on the influence of travel vlogs.

6. RECOMMENDATION

1. Factors Watching Travel Vlogs

1.1 Vloggers Attractiveness

Vloggers will enhance their communicating skills and sense of humor when making a vlog. They will respect and learn about the culture that they will visit. Their appearance on the camera should be well improved to gain more views.

1.2 Perceived Information Credibility

Vloggers should be more focused on delivering concrete information to the viewers about the details of the place that they are visiting rather than giving effective suggestions, so viewers will have ideas to have when they are still planning and watching travel vlogs. The visit can be more effective and save time by not having to find guides online.

1.3 Perceived Enjoyment

Vloggers/content creators should be more realistic and natural when filming a vlog. Creative thinking can help viewers to enjoy the vlog, relive their stress, and at the same time get ideas and credible sources of information when planning to travel.

1.4 Perceived Value for Money

Vloggers should highly suggest places to viewers that are worth every peso that they are spending, being honest about reviews of each place that they visit, like restaurants and hotels, that can largely benefit other travelers/viewers when they book their trip.

1.5 Perceived Usefulness

Vloggers should not stop looking for remote places that have the potential to grow. It can help not just viewers but also the tourism industry to grow. New places can be discovered with the help of vloggers who will reveal the true beauty of some other places that have not yet been discovered.

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